

Xanthenes from *Pinus roxburghii*

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Abstract : Two new xanthone identified as 1,5-dihydroxy-3,6,7-trimethoxy-8-allyloxyxanthone and 1-hydroxy-3,6-dimethoxy-2- β -D-glucopyranoxanthone have been isolated from the methanolic extract of the bark of *Pinus roxburghii* and the structure were established on the basis of spectroscopic data and chemical evidences.

Keywords : Xanthenes, *Pinus roxburghii*.

Pinus roxburghii belongs to family Pinaceae, is an ever-green tree distributed throughout in submontane to montane zone at an altitude of 900–2500 m. The tree yields oleoresin is a common ingredient of various ailments and the saw dust of plant is used in bronchitis and asthma¹. The plant is well-known for terpenoids² and fatty acids³. In this paper we have first time reported a xanthone glycoside and a prenylated xanthone from the bark of the plant.

Results and discussion

The aqueous methanolic extract of the plant afforded compound **1** as yellow sticky solid, gave Mg/HCl and Gibbs test positive. Its positive FAB-MS showed $[M]^+$ ion peak at m/z 402 consistent with molecular formula $C_{21}H_{22}O_8$. Its IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3260 (OH) and 1640 cm^{-1} (conjugated and chelated CO); UV at λ_{max} 269 nm showed presence of xanthone. No $AlCl_3$ induced shift observed in the UV spectrum suggesting the presence of a bulky group located *ortho* to the hydrogen bonded group⁴. The other significant peaks observed in its MS were at m/z 199 $[M-C_5H_8O]^+$, m/z 340, 309 and 292 corresponding to the loss of a prenyl, 3-OCH₃ and 2-OH groups, respectively. The ¹H NMR of **1** showed singlets at δ 12.4 and 9.8, exchangeable with D₂O indicating the presence of chelated hydroxyl at C-1 and a free hydroxyl. Two singlets (3H each) at δ 1.65 and 1.78, two doublets (2H each) at δ 5.09 (J 7.4 Hz) and 6.30 (J 7.4 Hz) supported the presence of the prenyloxy (3,3-dimethylallyloxy), while singlets (3H each) at δ 2.57, 3.44, 3.2 assigned for three methoxy groups.

Compound **2**, $C_{21}H_{22}O_{11}$, $[M]^+$ m/z 450 in FAB-MS (positive mode), give positive Sinoda and Gibbs colour

tests. It furnished peaks in FAB-MS at m/z 289, 272, 251 and 220 corresponding to the loss of ion peak of a sugar, one hydroxyl and two methoxyl groups. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR support the structure of **2** as a xanthone glycoside. Acid hydrolysis of **2** gave an aglycone (1,2-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxyxanthone⁵) and glucose (PC) as a glycone, by comparing the shift value of ¹³C and ¹H NMR. All NMR chemical shift values were assigned on the basis of decoupling and DEPT experiments.

Experimental

M.ps. were uncorrected, UV spectra were determined in MeOH with $AlCl_3$ shift reagent, IR recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 781 spectrometer, ¹H NMR were run at 300 MHz using TMS as internal standard and $CDCl_3$ as solvent, ¹³C NMR were recorded in 90 MHz using DMSO as solvent, EI-MS and FAB-MS on a JEOL JMS 700 Mstaion

spectrophotometer. Extracts were column chromatographed on silica gel (Qualigen, 60–120 mesh) and thin layer on silica gel G (Merck).

The bark of *Pinus roxburghii* were collected from Kandoliya, Pauri Garhwal and identified from Taxonomy Research Laboratory, HNB Garhwal University (Uttaranchal). The herbarium has been deposited in Department of Botany of this University. The air-dried and chopped bark (2.5 kg) was extracted with 90% ethanol (6 times). The total extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. The extract was successively partitioned with petroleum ether, methanol and butanol. Methanolic extract on CC in CHCl_3 -MeOH (9.1 : 0.8 \rightarrow 8.5 : 1.5) gave compound **1** and **2** in pure form and an impure compound which was not identified.

Compound 1 : Yellow sticky solid (MeOH- CHCl_3), m.p. 312–315 °C, FAB-MS 402 $[\text{M}]^+$, 371 $[\text{M}-\text{OCH}_3]^+$, 340 $[\text{M}-2 \times \text{OCH}_3]^+$, 292 $[\text{M}-(3 \times \text{OCH}_3 + \text{OH})]^+$, 283 $[\text{M}-(2 \times \text{OCH}_3 + 2 \times \text{OH})]^+$, 199 $[\text{M}-(3 \times \text{OCH}_3 + 2 \times \text{OH} + \text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O})]^+$; ^1H NMR (δ , CDCl_3) 7.5 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, H-2), 6.89 (d, J 8.6 Hz, H-4), 2.57 (3H, s, OMe), 3.9 (3H, s, OMe), 3.44 (3H, s, OMe), 12.4 (1H, s), 9.8 (1H, s), 1.39 (3H, s, H-4'), 1.4 (3H, s, H-5'), 5.09 (1H, bt, J 7.4 Hz, H-2'), 6.30 (2H, d, J 7.4 Hz, H-1'); ^{13}C NMR 161.6 (C-1), 99.0 (C-2), 164.7 (C-3), 94.2 (C-4), 145.9 (C-5), 148.2 (C-6), 148.5 (C-7), 160.0 (C-8a), 113.2 (C-8a), 176.7 (C-9), 112.7 (C-9a), 143.6 (C-10), 147.0 (C-11), 56.7 (OMe), 60.4 (OMe), 124.8 (C-1'), 122.6 (C-2'), 29.1 (C-3'), 15.14 (C-4'), 11.82 (C-5').

Compound 2 : Yellow crystals (MeOH), 290–300 °C, FAB-MS 452 $[\text{M} + 2\text{H}]^+$, 450 $[\text{M}]^+$, 289 $[\text{M} + 2\text{H}-162]^+$, 272 $[\text{M} + 2\text{H}-\text{OH}]^+$, 251 $[\text{M} + 2\text{H}-(\text{OH} + \text{OCH}_3)]^+$; UV

λ_{max} 245, 265, 322, 331, 385; IR ν_{max} 2945–3000 (OH), 1640 (CO); ^1H NMR 6.20 (1H, s, H-4), 6.60 (1H, s, H-5), 7.24 (2H, d, J 8.8 Hz), 3.27 (3H, s), 3.38 (3H, s), 12.50 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR 162.8 (C-1), 164.7 (C-2), 160.4 (C-3), 94.4 (C-4), 157.0 (C-5), 148.2 (C-6), 145.9 (C-7), 157.3 (C-8a), 114.3 (C-8), 176.4 (C-9), 112.0 (C-9a), 103.9 (C-10), 140.2 (C-11), 55.8 (OMe), 57.5 (OMe), 101.4 (C-1'), 73.1 (C-2'), 76.0 (C-3'), 69.9 (C-4'), 70.0 (C-5'), 60.30 (C-6').

Hydrolysis of compound 2 : Compound **2** (54 mg) was dissolved in 17% HCl in MeOH (50 ml) and the solution was refluxed for 5 h and the progress of reaction was monitored by TLC. After complete hydrolysis it was partitioned by EtOAc. The organic layer containing the aglycone was concentrated and the concentrate was chromatographed to get 1,2-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethoxyxanthone and the glycone part after neutralisation gave glucose (co PC and r_f value) with an authentic sample.

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